

Wadi'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Wadi'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Wadi'ah " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Wadi'ah based on the journals that have been collected. The results of the research show that there are 6 Mapping Research Topicss surrounding the Wadi'ah, namely: (1) The influence caused by the Bank Indonesia/SWBI Wadi'ah Certificate; (2) The influence caused by Wadi'ah's savings; (3) Views of Islamic law, positive law and legislation surrounding the Wadi'ah; (4) Efforts to develop the Wadi'ah; (5) Factors that influence public interest in the Wadi'ah; and (6) Other issues related to the Wadi'ah. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding the Wadi'ah, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Wadi'ah; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Ulama compiled the legal basis of the Qur'an regarding the Wadi'ah by considering the general purpose of the contract and matching it with verses relating to the issue of deposits. The Wadi'ah is one of the sharia principles that uses funding products in the sharia sector as regulated in DSN-MUI Fatwa No. 1 regarding Giro and DSN-MUI Fatwa No. 2 regarding Savings. These two fatwas generally provide for current and savings products that are based on wadi'ah, namely deposits that can be taken at any time without compensation requirements, except in the form of voluntary donations from the bank. Wadi'ahs are always available in every Islamic Financial Institution product, such as sharia banks and sharia cooperatives. Because of this, the Wadi'ah product has become a popular choice for people when entrusting assets or money. One type of Wadi'ah that may be implemented in Islamic Financial institutions is Wadi'ah yad dhamanah, which is used to utilize assets or money held by Islamic Financial institutions as a business or investment.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding the Wadi'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Wadi'ah, so that it can be a

reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding the Wadi'ah, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Islamic jurisprudence explains that the principle of deposit or savings which is commonly known in the banking world is called the al-wadi'ah principle. According to its etymology, al-wadi'ah means entrusting something that is not in the hands of its owner to be looked after. There are two meanings put forward by jurisprudence experts. First, in the opinion of the Hanafiyah School, al-wadi'ah is asking for help from other people to safeguard assets, either in a clear way, through actions or through gestures. Second, according to the opinion of the Malikiyah, Syafi'iyah and Hanabilah schools, al-wadi'ah means representing other people in guarding certain assets in a certain way.

Islamic Financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic Financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies in information science are studies that study the patterns of use of documents in literature or information sources in a particular subject. Bibliometrics consists of two types of research, namely descriptive studies and evaluative studies. Descriptive studies analyze the productivity of articles and other formats by examining authorship traits, such as the gender of the author, the type of author's work, the level of collaboration, the productivity of the institution where the author works, and the subject of the article. Evaluative studies analyze the use of created literature by counting the number of references or citations in research articles, books, or other formats. VOSviewer an improved computer program for creating and displaying

bibliometric maps. Publication maps can be displayed in several ways and functions, such as resizing, scrolling, and searching. In this way, articles can be mapped in more detail. VOSviewer presents and represents specific information about bibliometric graph maps.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Wadi’ah. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Wadi’ahs on Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Wadiyah " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Wadi’ah based on journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

In this chapter, we review research mapping on Wadi’ahs in Islamic Financial Institutions using VOSviewer bibliometric studies and Library Researchs. Based on search results on the Garuda website, we found 70 published article titles originating from accredited national journals.

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Wadi’ahs in Islamic Financial Institutions

The results of scientific research on Wadi’ahs in Islamic Financial Institutions from 2009 to 2022 show an increase in publications, especially in 2021 which reached 20 articles. However, in 2022, the number of article publications will decrease to only 15 articles. Even in 2010 and 2017, there were no articles discussing the Wadi’ah. This shows that research on the Wadi’ah is still minimal and does not always occur every year, with an average of 6 scientific publications on the Wadi’ah per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding the Wadi’ah by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publications	Year of Publication	Number of Publications
2009	1	2018	6
2012	1	2019	7
2013	3	2020	8
2014	3	2021	20
2015	5	2022	15
2016	1		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

In table 2, the 60 affiliates/institutions that published the most research articles regarding Wadi'ahs in Islamic Financial Institutions were obtained. Ad Diwan Journal, el-Amwal, El-Aswaq, Journal of Accounting and Investment, AKUNESA Accounting Journal, Journal of Economics, Management, Business and Accounting Review, Economic Journal-Qu, FEB Student Scientific Journal, Justisia Ekonomika Journal: Master of Sharia Economic Law, Monetary - Journal of Accounting and Finance is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research regarding the Wadi'ah, namely 2 articles.

Table 2. Affiliates/institutions publishing journals regarding the Wadi'ah

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Ad Diwan, el-Amwal, El-Aswaq, Journal of Accounting and Investment, AKUNESA Accounting Journal, Journal of Economics, Management, Business and Accounting Review, Economic Journal-Qu, FEB Student Scientific Journal, Journal of Justisia Ekonomika: Master of Sharia Economic Law, MONETARY - JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING AND FINANCE	2
ADLIYA: Journal of Law and Humanity, ACCURATE: Journal of Scientific Accounting FE UNIBBA, AL-ARBAH: Journal of Islamic Finance and Banking, Al-Azhar Journal of Islamic Economics, AL-INFAQ, Al-Kharaj: Journal of Sharia Economics, Finance & Business, Al-tsaman: Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, Al-Urban: Journal of Sharia Economics and Islamic Philanthropy, Assets: Scientific Journal of Accounting, Finance and Tax Sciences, Asy-Syir'ah: Journal of Sharia and Legal Sciences, At-Tauzi, Economics, Finance, Investment and Sharia (EQUITY): Journal of Islamic Economics, Az-Zarqa': Journal of Islamic Business Law, Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking, Economica: Journal of Islamic Economics, Economics of Business Management and Accounting (EBMA), El- Barka: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, Indonesian Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, Iqtishaduna: Scientific Journal of Sharia Economic Law Students, Islamic Economic and Business Journal, J-ESA (Journal of Sharia Economics), JAMMIAH (Scientific Journal of Sharia Economics Students), JIKEM: Journal of Computer Science, Economics and Management, JIMAT (Scientific Journal of Accounting Students) Undiksha, JIMMBA, JISA (Journal of Informatics and Science), JOURNAL OF COOPERATION AND MANAGEMENT, Journal of Islamic Economics and Social Science (JIESS), Journal of Accounting, Management and Digital Business, Bilal Journal: Halal Economic Business, Economic Journal of Management Science, Journal of Economics, Management, Accounting and Finance, JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS, MANAGEMENT, BUSINESS AND SOCIAL (EMBISS), JOURNAL OF SHARIA ECONOMIC LAW, Indonesian	1

Accounting Scientific Journal, Student Scientific Journal Sharia Banking (JIMPA), Islamic Investment Journal, Masharif al-Syariah Journal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Neraca Peradaban Journal, REKSA Journal: Financial Engineering, Sharia and Auditing, Research and Application Journal: Accounting and Management, LISAN AL-HAL: Journal of Development of Thought and Culture, Madani Syari'ah, MAXIMUM, Science Tower, Mukaddimah: Journal of Islamic Studies, PILAR, Proceedings of UMY Grace, Review of Islamic Economics and Finance (RIEF), Syntax Literate

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Furthermore, the most productive researchers researching Wadi'ahs are Ariska Widya Andriyanti, Barbara Gunawan, Emile Satia from Muhammadiyah University Yogyakarta who wrote 2 articles. Meanwhile, other researchers only wrote 1 journal article about the Wadi'ah.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding the Wadi'ah

Search results on the Garuda website found 70 research articles regarding Wadi'ahs at Islamic Financial Institutions in Indonesia. After that, the article is downloaded in RIS (Research Information Systems) form, input and reviewed using the VOSviewer tool. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments surrounding the Wadi'ah

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Wadi'ahs in Islamic Financial Institutions, divided into 7 clusters with 174 topics, are as follows:

- Cluster 1. Red covers 50 topics, namely : according, al Wadi'ah, application, aspect, bank, Bank Syariah Indonesia kcp Batang Toru, Bank Syariah Mandiri Maros Branch, banking, BMT, BMT al Azhari, company, contract, customer, development, DSN-MUI IV, employee, facility, field, field research, fiqh, implementation, independent sharia waste bank, industrial era, interview, Islamic law, management, marketing strategy, money, object, obstacle, party, person, price, principle, problem, product, regulation, researcher, sharia bank, my savings product, strategy, student, time, trust, understanding, uspps BMT sunan drajat, Wadi'ah, wadiah saving product, wadiah yad dhamanah, wadiah yad dhamanah contract.
- Cluster 2. Green covers 38 topics, namely : Bank Indonesia, BUS, coefficient, f test, factor, financing, giro wadiah, Indonesian Islamic banking statistics, inflation, influence, level, method, mudharabah deposit, multiple linear regression analysis, net profit, sig value, OJK, operating expense, profit sharing, PT Bank Sumut, research method, rupiah exchange rate, sample, secondary data, sig, significance level, significance effect, spss, spss software, student interest, BRI sharia, t test, value, variable, variable, wadiah bonuse, wadiah saving, wadiah savings.
- Cluster 3. Blue covers 24 topics, namely : amount, asset, cash, independent variable, interest, Islamic bank, murabahah financing, NPF, murabahah financing, positive effect, profit margin, promotion, public, quality, questionnaire, return, ROA, wadiah bank Indonesia certificate, service, service quality, Surat Wadiah Bank Indonesia, SWBI, third party fund, Wadiah savings account.
- Cluster 4. Yellow covers 22 topics, namely : Bank BNI syariah registered with OJK, customer decision, data collection technique, decision, effect, financial services authority, increase, mudharabah, mudharabah contract, musyarakah contract, observation, financial services authority, profitability, psychological factor, PT Bank BNI syariah, quantitative research, research, respondent, respondent, SAK, significant value, t value.
- Cluster 5. Purple covers 19 topics, namely : account, Wadi'ah, Bank Negara Indonesia, Bank Sumut Syariah Katamso, fees, BNI, BSI, client, deposit, IB Makbul Hajj savings product, information, qualitative, payment, point, qualitative method, saving, sharia, savings, deposit.
- Cluster 6. Blue covers 11 topics, namely : bonus, conventional banking, funds, interest rate, Islamic banking, keywords, service quality, mudharabah principle, owner, savings product, wadiah.
- Cluster 7. Orange covers 10 topics, namely : Mandiri sharia bank, consumer knowledge, sharia banking, Persero, GDP gross domestic product, Wadiah savings, TBK KCP Ciamis, F test, T test, interview.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Influence Caused by Bank Indonesia Wadiah Certificate (SWBI)

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 11 research topics regarding the influence of SWBI on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, Net Asset Value (NAV) of Sharia Mutual Funds. SWBI can influence the NAV of Sharia Mutual Funds because SWBI can be an investment

alternative for sharia mutual fund investment managers. If a sharia bank has SWBI with competitive interest rates, then investment managers can use it to increase returns on sharia mutual fund investments. This can have a positive impact on the NAV of Sharia Mutual Funds, because higher returns from SWBI will increase the investment value of sharia mutual fund unit holders.

Second, Mudharabah savings. SWBI can have an impact on Mudharabah deposits because Islamic banks can use funds from SWBI to increase their liquidity. If an Islamic bank has adequate liquidity, this will enable the bank to offer better returns on Mudharabah deposits. Thus, the influence of SWBI on Mudharabah savings can increase the returns received by customers.

Third, Islamic bank profits. SWBI can affect sharia bank profits because by using SWBI, sharia banks can increase their liquidity at lower costs. With higher liquidity, Islamic banks can make more profitable investments or provide greater financing to customers. This can have a positive impact on Islamic bank revenues and profits.

Fourth, Murabahah financing in sharia banking. SWBI can influence Murabahah financing in sharia banking because with SWBI, sharia banks can obtain higher liquidity. With sufficient liquidity, Islamic banks can offer Murabahah financing at competitive interest rates and provide easy access to financing for customers. This can encourage an increase in Murabahah financing and overall sharia banking business activities.

Fifth, profit sharing financing. SWBI can influence profit sharing financing in sharia banking. With SWBI, Islamic banks can increase their liquidity by utilizing this certificate. This excess liquidity can be used to provide profit sharing financing to customers. Sharia banks can use funds from SWBI to carry out broader financing and provide more product choices for customers who need financing based on the profit sharing principle.

Sixth, profit sharing ratio. The profit sharing ratio is the distribution of profits between sharia banks as fund providers and customers as fund users in profit sharing financing. SWBI can influence the profit sharing ratio because with SWBI, Islamic banks have additional sources of liquidity that can be used to provide profit sharing financing to customers. Sharia banks can determine a more competitive or flexible profit sharing ratio, so they can attract more customers to use their profit sharing financing products.

Seventh, the Ju'alah contract. The Ju'alah contract is a sale and purchase agreement with a reward or reward for a service or good that has been provided. SWBI can influence the Ju'alah contract because with SWBI, sharia banks can obtain higher liquidity. With adequate liquidity, sharia banks can provide financing to customers who need it in Ju'alah contracts with rewards or gifts in accordance with the agreement between the bank and the customer.

Eighth, Return On Assets (ROA). SWBI can influence Return On Assets (ROA) of Islamic banks. With SWBI, Islamic banks can obtain additional liquidity which can be used to increase the effective use of their assets. Islamic banks can use funds from SWBI to provide financing or make investments that generate higher returns. This can increase the ROA of Islamic banks because the income generated from assets that are used efficiently can increase.

Ninth, Third Party Funds (DPK). SWBI can affect third party funds (DPK) of sharia banks. DPK is the amount of funds received by sharia banks from customers and is one of the sources of bank funding. With SWBI, Islamic banks can obtain additional liquidity which can be used to increase DPK. Customers can save their funds in SWBI because this instrument is guaranteed by Bank

Indonesia. This can increase customer confidence and encourage them to deposit more funds in sharia banks, thereby potentially increasing sharia bank deposits.

Tenth, Financing To Deposit Ratio (FDR). FDR measures the proportion of financing provided by Islamic banks to the funds they receive from customers. SWBI can influence FDR because with additional liquidity from SWBI, Islamic banks have more funds that can be used to provide financing. If Islamic banks use SWBI effectively, FDR can increase because the financing provided by the bank will increase, while the funds received from customers remain unchanged or do not change significantly.

Eleventh, Non Performing Financing (NPF). NPF indicates the level of financing that is experiencing payment problems or is stuck. SWBI can influence NPF because with additional liquidity from SWBI, Islamic banks can strengthen credit risk management and manage financing better. Islamic banks can use funds from SWBI to provide more credible financing to customers and reduce NPF risk. With better risk management, Islamic banks can control NPF and minimize its negative impact on financial performance.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around The Influence of Wadiah Savings

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 15 research topics regarding the influence that Wadiah savings have on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, Mudharabah Muthlaqah. The influence of Wadiah Savings on Mudharabah Muthlaqah, which is a profit sharing mechanism between the bank and customers, can be positive or negative depending on how the bank manages the funds received through Wadiah Savings. The following are some of the possible impacts: (1) Potential Source of Funds: Wadiah Savings can provide a stable source of funds for sharia banks to be used for financing through Mudharabah Muthlaqah. Banks can use these funds to run businesses and earn profits. (2) Portfolio Growth: With Wadiah Savings, banks can increase the amount of funds available to be placed in profitable Mudharabah Muthlaqah projects. This can contribute to the growth of the Islamic banking portfolio and the potential for increased profits. (3) Risk Management: In Mudharabah Muthlaqah, the bank acts as a fund manager and shares risks with customers. Wadiah Savings can provide banks with greater financial stability, thereby enabling banks to better manage risks in Mudharabah Muthlaqah projects.

Second, competitive advantage. Wadiah Savings can have a positive impact on the competitive advantage of Islamic banks in the following ways: (1) Product Diversification: By offering Wadiah Savings, Islamic banks can expand their product range. This allows banks to attract customers with different preferences and needs, and increase their market share. Product diversification can provide a competitive advantage for Islamic banks in competition with conventional banks. (2) Customer Trust: Wadiah Savings is based on the principle of trust between customers and sharia banks. Customers can feel safer in saving and managing their funds through Wadiah Savings compared to conventional banking products. This trust can give Islamic banks an advantage in retaining customers and winning market share. (3) Sharia Compliance: Islamic banks offering Wadiah Savings demonstrate their commitment to sharia principles. This may attract customers who are looking for a banking alternative that is in line with their religious principles. In this context, Islamic banks can

gain a competitive advantage by targeting market segments that specifically seek Islamic banking products.

Third, profitability of Islamic banking. The influence of Wadiah Savings on the profitability of sharia banking can occur through the following mechanisms: (1) Source of Income: Wadiah Savings can be a source of income for sharia banks through financing provided through the Mudharabah Muthlaqah product. With the increasing amount of funds available through Wadiah Savings, banks have the opportunity to generate greater income from their business operations. (2) Operational Efficiency: With Wadiah Savings, Islamic banks can obtain fund stability that can be used to finance Mudharabah Muthlaqah projects. This can help banks manage resources and improve operational efficiency. Better operational efficiency can contribute to increased profitability. (3) Customer Trust and Loyalty: Wadiah Savings can strengthen customer trust in sharia banks. High trust can increase customer loyalty, which in turn can generate long-term profits for Islamic banks through repeat business and positive recommendations to others.

Fourth, interest rates. Wadiah Savings is a banking product based on the Wadiah principle, where customers entrust their funds to the bank and the bank acts as a trustee of these funds. As a form of appreciation for the trust given, the bank provides rewards to customers in the form of gifts or fixed profits that have been previously agreed upon. The impact of Wadiah Savings on interest rates may vary depending on the policies of the bank offering this product. In many cases, Wadiah Savings bonuses tend to be lower than interest rates on conventional savings or deposits. This can be caused by product characteristics that provide higher protection to customers, but at the same time, also provide lower rewards.

Fifth, customer behavior. Wadiah Savings can have an influence on customer behavior because of the underlying Wadiah principles. Customers who choose Wadiah Savings usually have the need to store funds with a high level of security, where the bank is responsible as a trustee. In this case, customers may be more inclined to choose stability and security over the potential for higher profits. This choice can influence customer behavior in several ways, such as increasing awareness of financial security and stability, and reducing the risks associated with riskier investments. However, each customer can also have different financial preferences and goals, so the influence of Wadiah Savings on customer behavior can vary individually.

Sixth, net profit. The effect of Wadiah Savings on a bank's net profit can depend on a number of factors, including the scale of the bank's operations, the amount of funds placed in Wadiah Savings, and the management of risks associated with this product. Wadiah Savings usually provides fixed rewards or prizes to customers, which can be considered as costs that must be borne by the bank. If the bank has a significant amount of funds in Wadiah Savings, these rewards can affect overall net profit. However, this influence must also be seen in the context of the bank's business strategy and diversification of income sources. Some banks may rely on Wadiah Savings as one of their main sources of income, while others may utilize a variety of banking products and services to achieve optimal net profits.

Seventh, Murabahah margin income. Wadiah Savings is a type of sharia banking product where customers deposit funds with the bank for storage and security purposes. In Wadiah savings, the bank acts as a trustee who is responsible for the funds deposited by the customer. Therefore, Wadiah savings generally do not have a direct influence on Murabahah margin income.

Murabahah margin income is one component of sharia bank income which comes from profits obtained from buying and selling goods transactions. In the Murabahah scheme, the bank buys goods desired by the customer and sells them to the customer at an agreed price, including a previously determined profit. This profit is the Murabahah margin income for the bank.

Eighth, Wadiah bonus. Wadiah bonuses are usually given by sharia banks to customers as compensation for funds deposited in Wadiah savings. This bonus is a bank policy which can vary from one bank to another. In this case, the Wadiah bonus can have a positive influence on customers, because customers will receive additional rewards from the bank for their savings. However, Wadiah bonuses are generally not directly related to Murabahah margin income, because these bonuses are more of an incentive for customers to choose and maintain Wadiah savings at the bank.

Ninth, Murabahah receivables. Murabahah receivables are the amount of bills that sharia banks must receive from customers who buy goods through the Murabahah scheme. When a customer buys goods, the bank provides financing using a Murabahah buying and selling scheme, and the customer is expected to pay the price of the goods within the agreed time period. Wadiah Savings does not directly affect Murabahah receivables, because the two are different products and concepts. However, savings in Wadiah savings can be used by the bank to finance Murabahah transactions to other customers. In this case, Wadiah savings can act as a source of funds for banks to expand their Murabahah financing portfolio, which in turn can influence the amount of Murabahah receivables owned by the bank.

Tenth, Murabahah financing. Wadiah savings do not directly affect Murabahah financing. Murabahah financing is a sale and purchase transaction of goods between the bank and the customer with an agreed scheme, where the bank buys the goods desired by the customer and sells them to the customer at a predetermined profit. Wadiah Savings, as a product for storing and securing funds, is generally not directly related to Murabahah financing.

Eleventh, Mudharabah financing. Wadiah savings do not directly affect Mudharabah financing. Wadiah Savings is more related to savings and securing funds, while Mudharabah financing involves business financing and profit sharing. However, banks can use savings in Wadiah savings as a source of funds to finance Mudharabah financing to customers who need it.

Twelfth, Maqashid Shariah Index. Wadiah Savings, as a sharia banking product, generally has the aim of providing a safe place to store funds and generate halal profits in accordance with sharia principles. Although Wadiah savings itself may not be directly linked to the Maqashid Shariah Index, the bank offering the product may have policies or other investment instruments that can be measured through the index. Therefore, banks can use the Maqashid Shariah Index as a guide for compiling their investment portfolios in accordance with sharia principles, including in terms of Murabahah financing, Mudharabah financing, and other products offered.

Thirteenth, financial performance. Wadiah Savings, as a sharia banking product, can influence the overall financial performance of sharia banks. The amount of funds stored in Wadiah savings can be a factor that influences bank liquidity, because banks use these funds for operational and financing activities. If the bank is successful in attracting large amounts of funds through Wadiah's savings, this could increase the bank's liquidity and potentially strengthen its financial performance. However, it is also important to consider appropriate policies and risk management so that liquidity can be managed well.

Fourteenth, income. Wadiah savings generally have a limited impact on sharia bank revenues. Customers who use Wadiah savings tend to deposit funds for the purpose of safekeeping and security, so that the rewards received by customers (such as Wadiah bonuses) can become a component of the bank's income. However, income from Wadiah savings is usually insignificant compared to the bank's main sources of income, such as income from financing and investments.

Fifteenth, sharia banking liabilities. Wadiah Savings is a type of sharia banking liability. Sharia banking liabilities are financial obligations owed by banks to customers and other parties. In this case, Wadiah savings represent funds placed by customers with the bank as deposits that can be withdrawn at any time. These funds become part of the bank's liabilities and the bank has an obligation to maintain the security and availability of these funds in accordance with the Wadiah principle. The existence of Wadiah savings as a bank liability can provide a source of funding for sharia banks. Banks can use funds placed in Wadiah savings to finance their operational activities, including Murabahah financing, Mudharabah and other investment activities. Therefore, Wadiah savings can influence the structure and composition of Islamic banking liabilities by providing funds that can be used to finance bank operational activities.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Views of Islamic Law, Positive Law and Legislation surrounding the Wadi'ah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 10 research topics regarding views of Islamic law, positive law and Wadi'ah legislation on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, the implementation of the Wadi'ah. In Islamic law, the Wadi'ah is a form of agreement for the security or custody of assets between two parties, namely wadi' (custodian) and mustawda' (custodian). In the Wadi'ah, the wadi' is responsible for looking after and looking after the assets entrusted to him by the mustawda' without any specified compensation or remuneration. From a legal perspective, the implementation of the Wadi'ah is considered valid and permitted in Islamic law. However, the party acting as wadi' has an obligation to guard the property in good faith and is responsible for losses caused by negligence or mistakes made in guarding the property.

Second, the implementation of the Wadiah Yad Dhamanah agreement. The Wadiah Yad Dhamanah contract is an expansion of the Wadi'ah which includes additional obligations for the wadi'. In the Wadiah Yad Dhamanah contract, the wadi' is not only responsible for guarding and maintaining the property, but also provides guarantees for losses that may occur related to the property. In this case, the implementation of the Wadiah Yad Dhamanah agreement is also considered valid in Islamic law, because it adds a broader aspect of responsibility for the wadi'. By providing a guarantee, wadi' becomes the party fully responsible for any losses that may occur, as long as the losses are not caused by things beyond wadi''s control.

Third, the principle of worship as a legal solution. The principle of *ibahah* is a concept in Islamic law that emphasizes leniency or tolerance in dealing with problems that require legal decisions. This principle can be used as a legal solution in situations that do not have specific rules or provisions in Islamic law. In this context, the principle of *ibahah* can be applied to resolve problems or situations that are not covered explicitly in Islamic law. This principle

requires a deep understanding of the values and objectives of Islamic law as well as considering the interests and benefits of Muslims in making legal decisions.

Fourth, the sharia level. The concept of “sharia level” refers to the extent to which an activity or product can be declared to be in accordance with the principles of Islamic law or sharia. Sharia levels can be applied in various contexts, such as banking, investment, insurance, or other financial products. Legal views regarding the level of sharia vary depending on the point of view and interpretation of the school or legal approach used. Generally, in Islamic law, an activity or product can be considered compliant with sharia if it meets basic principles such as the prohibition of *riba* (interest), *gharar* (excessive uncertainty), *maysir* (gambling), and the prohibition of transactions that violate the principles of justice. Assessment of the sharia level is often carried out by bodies or institutions that specialize in sharia assessment, such as fatwa boards or sharia supervisory institutions. They provide sharia certification or labels for products or activities that are deemed to meet sharia criteria. However, differences of opinion and judgment may occur between various sharia authorities.

Fifth, practice giving bonuses/gifts. In Islamic law, giving bonuses or gifts is generally considered legal and permissible, as long as they do not violate sharia principles. These principles include the prohibition of *riba* (interest), *maysir* (gambling), *gharar* (excessive uncertainty), and the prohibition of transactions that violate the principles of justice. In a business context, giving bonuses or gifts to employees or customers can be done as a form of appreciation or incentive. However, in its application, it is necessary to pay attention to applicable sharia rules and principles, such as not giving bonuses that originate from usury or do not contain elements of gambling.

Sixth, administrative costs. The legal view regarding administrative costs in Islamic law reflects the principles of justice and proportionality. In various transactions or services that involve administration fees, the basic principle that must be considered is the absence of abuse or exploitation. In practice, the administration fees charged must be reasonable and proportional to the services provided. Such costs must not exceed the limits permitted by sharia. The principle of justice also requires that administrative costs not be used as a tool to harm or burden other parties unfairly.

Seventh, deposit insurance. In Islamic law, deposit guarantees can be seen from the perspective of two things: guaranteeing deposits within financial institutions (such as banks) and guaranteeing deposits between parties to a transaction. In the context of financial institutions, several Islamic countries have deposit guarantee schemes that are similar to deposit guarantee schemes in conventional financial institutions. The purpose of deposit insurance is to protect customers or depositors from losses that may arise if a financial institution experiences financial difficulties or goes bankrupt. This deposit guarantee can provide a sense of trust and stability in the financial system. In other transactions, deposit guarantees can be carried out in the form of agreements between the parties involved. For example, in a *Wadi'ah*, the *wadi'* acts as guarantor for the assets entrusted to the *mustawda'*. This provides protection to the *mustawda'* against losses that may arise if the *wadi'* is negligent or does not fulfill its obligations in safeguarding the property.

Eighth, writ of achievement. Default in Islamic law refers to the violation or non-compliance with contractual obligations. When one party does not fulfill the obligations agreed upon in the contract, it can be categorized as a breach of contract. Islamic law recommends upholding the principles of justice and

compliance with contractual agreements. If a default occurs, the Islamic legal view emphasizes the importance of resolving the conflict in a fair manner and based on the principles of justice. The party affected by default has the right to request compensation or fulfillment of obligations that have not been fulfilled. In practice, default resolution can be carried out through mediation, negotiation, or through legal processes in accordance with applicable sharia principles.

Ninth, opening an account for minors. Legal views on opening accounts for minors vary depending on the interpretation of Islamic law adopted. Some views allow opening an account in the name of a minor with the supervision and authority of a parent or legal guardian. The main principle that must be considered is the interests and benefits of the child. If opening an account is considered to provide benefits and protect the rights of children, then it is acceptable from the perspective of Islamic law. However, it is important to ensure that the use and management of the account remains within limits in accordance with sharia principles. Parents or guardians acting on behalf of minors are responsible for maintaining the security and legality of the assets in the account.

Tenth, status of contract changes. In Islamic law, changes to agreements or contracts can occur in certain situations. However, changes to the contract must be carried out taking into account the principles of justice and mutual agreement between the parties involved. The view of Islamic law regarding contract changes tends to provide flexibility, as long as it does not violate established sharia principles. The principles of fairness, voluntary agreements, and transparency in contract changes are important considerations. In practice, if there is a change to the contract, it is necessary to ensure that the change is made in good faith and does not violate applicable sharia principles.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Wadi'ah Development Efforts

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 8 research topics surrounding efforts to develop Wadi'ahs for Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, designing the website interface. In the context of Wadi'ahs, website interface design refers to the process of creating visual displays and interactions that make it easier for users to interact with platforms or services that offer products or services based on Wadi'ahs. The interface design of this website must consider aspects of optimal user experience, conformity with sharia principles in the wadiah context, as well as user functional needs such as account registration, product selection, and clear display of information.

Second, database. Database in the context of Wadi'ahs refers to the storage and management of information related to contracts, transactions and customer data that use wadiah services. This database plays an important role in ensuring the security, integrity and availability of information needed to carry out the Wadi'ah process well. Information stored in the database may include customer identity data, balances, transaction history and other related information required for administration and reporting.

Third, the administration of opening a new account via online. Administration of opening a new account online for a Wadi'ah refers to the process of managing and processing data related to opening a wadiah account online or via an online platform. This administration process includes verifying the identity of prospective customers, collecting required documents, assessing

customer eligibility, and creating an account in accordance with the terms and conditions of the Wadi'ah. This administration is carried out electronically to simplify and speed up the account opening process and enable customers to access services more efficiently.

Fourth, accounting records. Accounting records in Wadi'ahs involve the process of collecting, processing and reporting financial information related to wadiah transactions. This recording includes recording customer deposits and withdrawals, interest payments (if applicable), as well as relevant financial reporting. The purpose of accounting records is to ensure transparency and accuracy of financial information, as well as comply with applicable reporting requirements. Accounting records also help in monitoring the financial performance of companies carrying out Wadi'ahs and provide a clear understanding of the financial position and business results related to the Wadi'ah.

Fifth, community participation. Community participation in Wadi'ahs refers to the involvement of individuals or groups in using services or products based on Wadi'ahs. In this context, community participation may involve the use of wadiah accounts, wadiah investments, or other financial services based on wadiah principles. Community participation is important to increase the use of Wadi'ahs as a sharia-compliant alternative and promote an economy based on justice and mutually beneficial agreements.

Sixth, marketing strategy for Wadi'ah products. The marketing strategy for Wadi'ah products involves planning and implementing steps to introduce, promote and sell products based on Wadi'ahs to the target market. This strategy includes identifying the right market segments, developing effective marketing messages, selecting relevant distribution channels, and using appropriate marketing methods such as advertising, promotions, digital marketing activities, and so on. The aim of the marketing strategy is to increase public awareness and interest in Wadi'ah products, so as to attract potential customers and expand market share.

Seventh, strategy for raising funds for Wadi'ah products. The strategy for raising funds in Wadi'ah products involves efforts to attract funds from the public or investors who want to utilize services or products based on Wadi'ahs. This strategy includes identifying target markets, developing products that are attractive to potential investors, preparing investment programs in accordance with wadiah principles, and effective communication about the benefits and potential profits of Wadi'ah products to potential investors. An effective fund raising strategy can help increase the amount of funds collected in Wadi'ah products and support sustainable business development.

Eighth, Wadi'ah fund management strategy. The fund management strategy in a Wadi'ah refers to the steps taken to optimize the use of funds collected from customers or investors. This strategy includes determining appropriate fund allocation, careful risk management, developing an investment portfolio in accordance with wadiah principles, as well as monitoring and evaluating investment performance periodically. The fund management strategy aims to maintain the security and growth of funds entrusted to wadiah service providers, as well as ensuring compliance with applicable sharia principles.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors that Influence Community Interest in the Wadi'ah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 16 research topics surrounding factors that influence public interest in

Wadi'ahs on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Religiosity; (2) Service; (3) Product Marketing Strategy; (4) Knowledge; (5) Savings Benefits; (6) Product Quality; (7) Nabasah Perception; (8) Facilities; (9) Employees; (10) Community Perspective; (11) Point of Purchase (POP); (12) 3A Attitude (Attitude, Attention, and Action) Based on Sharia; (13) Brand Image; (14) Student Understanding; (15) Al-Qur'an Surah Al-Baqarah verse 282; and (16) Product Mechanism.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Other Issues Relating to the Wadi'ah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 7 Research topics around other issues related to the Wadi'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, profit sharing income. Profit sharing income in a Wadi'ah refers to the profit or income obtained by the wadiah service provider based on the results of business or investments made using funds entrusted by the customer. In a Wadi'ah, this profit or income is shared between the wadiah service provider and the customer in accordance with a previously determined agreement. Profit sharing is a mechanism for sharing risks and business results that applies in Wadi'ahs, where profits and losses resulting from the use of funds are shared fairly between both parties.

Second, urabahah margin income. _ _ Murabahah margin income in a Wadi'ah refers to the profit obtained by the wadiah service provider from buying and selling assets or goods using the murabahah scheme. In a murabahah transaction, the wadiah service provider buys assets or goods requested by the customer and sells them to the customer at a price that includes a profit margin. This murabahah margin income is a source of income for wadiah service providers and is part of the profits obtained in their operations.

Third, Ijarah rental income. Ijarah rental income in a Wadi'ah refers to the income earned by a wadiah service provider from renting assets or goods to customers using an ijarah scheme. In an ijarah contract, the wadiah service provider buys assets or goods requested by the customer and rents them to the customer with an agreed rental payment. This ijarah rental income is a source of income for wadiah service providers and is a reward for the use of assets or goods by customers during the rental period.

Fourth, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) income. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) income in the Wadi'ah refers to the economic contribution made by the financial sector based on the principles of the Wadi'ah to the total economic value of a country. GDP measures the total added value of the economy from all sectors, including the financial sector which involves Wadi'ahs. In this context, GDP income reflects the contribution of the wadiah-based financial sector to overall economic growth, including through investment, financing and financial services activities carried out on wadiah principles.

Fifth, Wadiah's savings funds. Wadiah savings funds refer to funds saved by customers or deposits placed with financial institutions that carry out Wadi'ahs. These funds are managed by financial institutions as wadiah service providers, who are responsible for maintaining their security and sustainability. Wadiah savings funds function as a means for customers to store and secure their funds, with the hope that these funds will be available whenever needed and remain safe as long as they are under the supervision of the wadiah service provider.

Sixth, bonus level. _ The bonus level in a Wadi'ah refers to additional awards or rewards given to customers by wadiah service providers as incentives

or appreciation for the use of their products or services. Bonus levels can take the form of rewards in the form of cash, loyalty points, discounts, prizes or other benefits given to customers based on certain criteria or achievements. This bonus aims to encourage customers to continue using Wadi'ah services or products provided by financial institutions, as well as strengthening relationships and loyalty between customers and wadiah service providers.

Seventh, inflation towards SWBI. Inflation on Bank Indonesia Wadiah Sukuk (SWBI) refers to the effect of inflation on wadiah sukuk instruments issued by Bank Indonesia. SWBI is a financial instrument issued by Bank Indonesia with the aim of regulating the amount of money circulating in the market and controlling the inflation rate. Inflation is a general and persistent increase in the prices of goods and services in an economy. If inflation occurs, the nominal value of the Bank Indonesia Wadiah Sukuk may experience depreciation relative to the purchasing power of money because the prices of goods and services increase. Therefore, inflation can affect the value and performance of SWBI as an investment instrument.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Wadi'ahs on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) The influence caused by the Bank Indonesia/SWBI Wadiah Certificate; (2) The influence caused by Wadiah's savings; (3) Views of Islamic law, positive law and legislation surrounding the Wadi'ah; (4) Efforts to develop the Wadi'ah; (5) Factors that influence public interest in the Wadi'ah; and (6) Other issues related to the Wadi'ah.

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